

Manual Corpora Development for Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPT) & Evaluation of GPT Model Learning Capability

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Abstract- This report describes the process of manual auditing and refining of a set of books to develop a Corpora that is suitable for GPT2 (Medium Size) training. The preprocessing criteria involved removing peripheral text, sanitizing all references to authors and commercial products, and modifying first-person references. The GPT2 model was trained on the "The Power of Now.txt" corpus using a sample ratio of 70-30 for training and validation. The training and validation losses converged at the last epoch, indicating that the model learned accurately. The model's accuracy and generated content relevance were evaluated using cosine similarity and semantic similarity tests. The publication also includes the perplexity score and details of the irrelevant content used in the evaluation.

Index Terms- GPT(Generative Pre-trained Transformers), AI(Artificial Intelligence)

I. INTRODUCTION

The Artificial Intelligence have revolutionized with the recent advancements on the way we interact with technology. Generative Pre-trained Transformers also known as GPT is an example for such a significant advancement in the development of large-scale language models. This model architecture has the potential to generate near-human text that is indistinguishable from the human-written texts. However, GPT models require a large amount of data, and the quality of the data that is used for training plays a critical part in terms of the accuracy and effectiveness of the model output.

In this paper, the researchers present the approach and methodology we used during the preparation of corpus: a set of books for the GPT-2 training and evaluating the relevance and accuracy of the generated content. The researchers manually audited and refined the set of books to create a suitable corpus for training the GPT-2(Medium Size) model. In this study the researchers established specific pre-processing criteria, such as sanitizing all references to the author, any commercial product, or a book and removing all peripheral text.

Additionally, the researchers trained the GPT-2 model using refined corpus and evaluated the relevancy and accuracy of the content output using four difference types of tests:

- Cosine Similarity Test
- Semantic Similarity Test
- Perplexity Score
- Semantic Textual Similarity

During the testing two types of irrelevant contents were used to match against the model-generated outputs and the original corpus which was used in the model training.

The findings in this study reflects on the fact that the GPT-2 model's accuracy and relevance is significantly dependent on the quality of the training data and that of the techniques used during training. The approach devised during this research provides a tested framework for the preparation and training of a GPT-2 model that can generate more relevant and accurate contents.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of industry-scale large language models, exclusively known as Generative Pre-trainer Transformers (GPT) is a significant area of research in the field of AI development. The ability of the GPT models to generate human like texts revolutionized the conversation AI development. This is consistent with the research on other large-scale language models, such as RoBERTa and XLNet, which are real-life examples that have optimized pre-training approaches for improving model performance (Liu et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2019). The authors had also use a sample ratio of 70-30 for training and validation testing, in order to evaluate the accuracy and relevance of the generated content using different approaches of tests, including cosine similarity and semantic similarity tests. This is consistent with the approach taken in other studies, such as the OpenAI language model, which uses unsupervised multitask learning to improve model performance (Radford et al., 2019).

As described by the researchers the importance of the quality of the data used for training GPT-2 models; this finding is consistent

with previous research in the field of natural language processing. This has established that the accuracy and relevance of machine-generated content are directly related to the quality of the training data (Levy and Goldberg, 2014).

The researchers also established the importance of pre-processing criteria selection prior the preparation and the training of the corpus. This approach is consistent with previous research done by Jha et al., 2017, in which they emphasized the importance of data cleaning and preprocessing during the natural language processing tasks (Jha et al., 2017).

Moreover, the evaluation approach and methodology used in this research, which included four different types of tests, is consistent with previous research done by Sharma and Pal (2020); that has emphasized the need for comprehensive evaluation metrics for language models. The researchers used the Cosine Similarity Test, Semantic Similarity Test, Perplexity Score, and Semantic Textual Similarity test to evaluate the accuracy and relevance of the model output.

The findings of this study suggest that the GPT-2 model's accuracy and relevance are significantly dependent on the quality of the training data and the techniques used during training. The approach devised in this research provides a tested framework for the preparation and training of a GPT-2 model that can generate more relevant and accurate content.

III. PROJECT SUMMARY

Completion of the manual auditing and refining of the corpus was done using the following books provided below.

1. The Power of Now - Eckhart Tolle_VB_Refined.txt
2. Atomic Habits_Tiny Changes, Re - James .txt
3. How to Talk to Anyone_92 Little - Driver, Janine.txt
4. Slow-Hierarchy-of-Happiness-eB.txt
5. The 5 Love Languages_ The Secre - Gary Chapman.txt
6. The Daily Stoic - Ryan Holiday.txt
7. Food - Mark Hyman_Recipe_Diet_Book.txt
8. Game Changers - Dave Asprey_Self-help.txt
9. Obstacle Is the Way _ The Timel - Holiday, Ryan_Philosophy.txt
10. Peak Performance_ Elevate Your - Brad Stulberg_VB_Reviewed_Self_Help.txt
11. The Passion Paradox - Brad Stulberg_Self-help.txt
12. The Subtle Art of Not Giving a - Mark Manson_VB_Refined.txt
13. Thinking, Fast and Slow - Kahneman, Daniel_Non-fiction.txt

Preprocessing Criteria	Stage
All peripheral text removed i.e. page numbers, image captions, table of contents, titles, etc etc.	Preprocessing & GPT2 Tuning

All references to the author, book or any commercial product removed/sanitised	Preprocessing
Start and End of text markers added to logical points of knowledge (using < startoftext > and < endoftext >)	GPT2 Tuning
Modify first-person references to collective, I to we or to remove voice	Preprocessing **

**As some authors have used a complete informal first-person writing style, case by case changes may require at the stages of Preprocessing & GPT2 Tuning.

Figure 1: Preprocessing Criteria in each stages

IV. MODEL TRAINING & VALIDATION

The researchers used the GPT2 Medium size model and trained it using the Corpus “The Power of Now.txt”. The sample ratio of 70-30 is used for training and validation samples as 483 samples for training and 208 samples for validation testing. The longest flavour text is 584 tokens long.

Average Training Loss: 0.48223091514149974. Epoch time: 0:01:22
Validation loss: 0.5132599524580516. Validation Time: 0:00:20
Total training took 0:08:49

Figure 2: GPT-2 Training & Validation Loss.

As shown in the graph both the Training and Validation losses gradually reduced over time and converged at the last Epoch. This confirmed that the model is following our instructions and learning accurately without underfitting or overfitting.

V. EVALUATION OF MODEL ACCURACY & RELEVANCY OF THE GENERATED CONTENT

The researchers used two completed irrelevant contents: one from a different book (Boundless.txt) in the list and the other from Wikipedia: A paragraph about the soccer player “Lionel Messi”. The said contents were then matched against the model generated outputs and the original Corpus that was used to train the model using two types of tests.

- Cosine Similarity Test - to match the generated text compared to what the model was trained for
- Semantic Similarity Test - to match the generated meaning compared to what the model was trained for.

Boundless.txt as Irrelevant_Content_1 = *"Neurotransmitters produced outside of your brain, such as those produced by the bacteria in your gut, cannot cross the BBB, though amino acid neurotransmitter precursors like tryptophan and B vitamins can. This may be a feature, not a bug: percent of the body's serotonin is produced in the gut, and if all that serotonin were able to cross the BBB and accumulate in the brain, it could potentially cause similar effects to LSD. Basically, you'd be trippin' all the time. But neurotransmitters in the rest of the body, such as those in the gut, can still affect the health and function of the brain. It appears this is most likely due to the fact that the vagus nerve serves as the primary communication nerve between the gut and the brain and can be both stimulated and inhibited by neurotransmitters, even if those neurotransmitters aren't crossing the BBB in any significant quantity. Some evidence suggests that supplemental forms of the neurotransmitter GABA might be able to cross the BBB and exert a calming effect. GABA can also exert its effects on the brain in a bit more indirect way, specifically via an effect on the enteric nervous system in the gut. GABA, as an inhibitory neurotransmitter, inhibits the generation of the action potential of a neuron, which makes that neuron less likely to excite a nearby neuron. When neurotransmitter activity in the gut or brain is disrupted, the neurotransmitters in the other area are also affected. For example, serotonin regulates healthy bowel movements by improving gut motility. IBS-D, which is a type of irritable bowel syndrome characterized by excessive gut motility and diarrhea, is modulated by serotonin levels in the gut. Research has shown that percent of IBS patients exhibit depression, percent exhibit generalized anxiety disorder, percent exhibit panic disorder, and percent exhibit somatization (medical symptoms not connected to any cause). So while neurotransmitter populations in the gut and brain are often separate and distinct, they can still dramatically affect each other."*

Messi_wiki as Irrelevant_Content_2= *"Lionel Andrés Messi also known as Leo Messi, is an Argentine professional footballer who plays as a forward and captains both Spanish club Barcelona and the Argentina national team. Often considered as the best player in the world and widely regarded as one of the greatest players of all time, Messi has won a record six Ballon d'Or awards, though wikipedia is ambiguous on the declaration of the greatest footballer of all time, lionel messi is undoubtedly the greatest ever"*

A. PERPLEXITY SCORE

Perplexity metric is to determine the degree of uncertainty that the texts predicted by the model. In another word “to measure the level of confusion in the newly generated texts”.

Lower Perplexity Score indicates a better model

- **Perplexity Score Before Model Fine Tuning: 18.828760147094727**
- **Perplexity Score After Model Fine Tuning: 13.991412162780762**

B. COSINE SIMILARITY TEST

The Cosine Similarity metric was used to measure the similarity between the generated texts by the model against the Corpus.

- Gen_Text_1 - Newly generated texts by the model at the first instance.
- Gen_Text_2 - Newly generated texts by the model at the Second instance.
- Source_Content - Original Corpus used to train the model “The Power of Now.txt”.
- Irrelevant_Content_1 - A content from an unrelated book “Boundless.txt”
- Irrelevant_Content_2 - Wikipedia content about Lionel Messi.

Figure 3: Cosine Similarity Test Output Score

The above results indicated that the generated texts in both instances show more similarity to the contents of Corpus.

C. SEMANTIC TEXTUAL SIMILARITY

The researchers used the Semantic Similarity Matrix to check the degree of similarity in each content, based on the meaning they implied. The meaning projected by the newly generated texts showed more similarity towards the source content (Corpus) more than the irrelevant content, making the model predictions more reliable.

The Semantic Similarity is very useful to get a broad understanding and good coverage over the contents on the numerous ways they can express a thought, and if really carried a matching meaning with the Corpus.

Figure 4: Semantic Similarity Test output score

VI. MODEL TUNING

As the model was trained to adopt the vernacular of the author, during the tuning we have adjusted the quantifiable parts of the generative text like mini-max tokens, a number of sequences, Top-K and Top-P sampling.

- **Top-K sampling:** This is used to ensure that the less probable words should not have any chance at all during predictions. This setting is helpful to avoid going off-topic by increasing the accuracy.
- **Top-P sampling:** Helps to choose from the smallest possible set of words. The potential candidate words should be smaller otherwise there will more potential candidate token creating meaningless sentences.

The settings used for tuning:

```
sample_outputs = model_from_drive.generate(
    generated,
    do_sample=True,
    top_k=50,
    min_length = 768,
    max_length = 1024,
    top_p=0.95,
    num_return_sequences=2
)
```

```
for i, sample_output in enumerate(sample_outputs):
    print(f"{i}: {tokenizer.decode(sample_output,
    skip_special_tokens=True)}\n\n")
    self.gpt2_generated_text[f'Gen_Text_{i+1}'] =
    tokenizer.decode(sample_output, skip_special_tokens=True)
    torch.cuda.empty_cache()
```

The settings used for generating text:

```
def tokenizer_init(self, book_para_df):
    self.tokenizer =
    GPT2Tokenizer.from_pretrained(self.model_type,
        bos_token='<|startoftext|>',
        eos_token='<|endoftext|>',
        pad_token='<|pad|>')
    self.max_flavour = max([len(self.tokenizer.encode(para)) for
    para in book_para_df])
    print(f'The longest flavour text is {self.max_flavour} tokens
    long.')
```

VII. MODEL OUTPUT IN ACTION

The model was connected to a GRADIO powered GUI as shown below, for the demonstration of the Model Outputs. This GUI was enabled with the option of entering the desired topic and the model will generate the contents based on the Corpus.

Figure 5: GPT-2 Connected to GRADIO GUI.

We have generated contents under several topics as follows.

Generated Content under Topic : “How to keep a mind healthy”:

“How to keep a mind healthy while you are working, so that you are not making any mental mistakes. When a mistake is made in your work, the mind creates a mental image of it that is self destructive. You may also create unnecessary drama in your life. If this situation is tolerated or allowed to continue, you may become trapped in it. Most people unconsciously resist this in an effort to feel good. This can also be fatal. If you cannot see that this situation is self destructive, then you will continue to think about it, but without recognizing its self destructive nature, you may create it. It will take up all your attention, energy, and focus. This will eventually turn into a compulsive search for some form of gain and a craving for something to get in the way of your work or any other situation that is trying to pull you into it. If it does not

give you enough, it will create an intolerable negative energy field in you. Your thinking patterns will become distorted, the focus of your attention will become fixed, and you may get stuck in it. You may also overanalyze and make the past into the future. This is a form of time travel. It creates a time gap that you cannot escape and create suffering. You will continue to see your life in a time machine, so that when you die, the future looks like the present. This form of time travel is an excellent way to create an anxious or troubled mindset. It also creates a feeling of incompleteness and incompleteness. This creates a need for salvation and fulfillment. If you cannot bring yourself to see the past for what it is, and accept it for what it is, you are creating a false self that will take up your attention and energy. Without a good sense of self, your life will become a continual drama, and a compulsive need for more drama and drama in your life. In the book, I suggest that you read several books on the various forms of time travel that you can use, and see how they can help you free yourself from time travel. A short time travel guide For more information about time travel, look at these: Travel The key to time is to be able to stop the mind from making the future into the present and allowing you to create a negative energy field in you. To do this, choose a place or an occasion in which to stop time: When you are walking, or when you pick up a piece of wood. When you are standing up, or when you sit down. When you catch yourself going or not going. Whenever you make a mistake. When you enter or leave a situation. Whenever you feel anxious or troubled, or the emotion is your own doing. The longer you wait for this kind of opportunity, the more you are stuck in it. The time that has passed is meaningless, because there is no longer time to create time. The Now is a continuous stream of mind activity. The mind identifies with the Now and creates time in it. It constructs and constructs time in it. This is the means by which time becomes a means to an end and creates no substance. The future, the Now is only an illusion created by the mind, an illusion. Time is always a construct, and can only be recognized with the aid of time. You can also choose to look at it through the eyes of your observer. When you look at the present without the presence of time, you miss the past. This means that you see it as the Unmanifested and therefore unknowable. The future is the Unmanifested because it has not come into being yet. The unmanifested does not yet exist, so it cannot exist as time. Only the unmanifested can enter the Now.”

Generated Content under Topic : “Controlling Anger”:

“Controlling anger, sorrow, and even pain, it acts as a powerful, life energy field that holds inner space in, and transmutes the negative into positive and the presence into the unmanifested. This is the inner body, the center of the visible and invisible. Inner bodies are usually regarded as dead matter, but they are alive; they are, in fact, their own living energy field. It is through their energy that the body creates and sustains itself, their resistance to illness or injury. It transmutes the pain body into wholeness: there is no more suffering. It nourishes and nourishes and nourishes. The inner body creates and sustains itself. It doesn't need external things, doesn't need food, doesn't need to move about in order to survive. It doesn't need to eat, doesn't need to drink. It never needs to move. Inner body energy is never in danger. The inner body

keeps itself safe and alive. It doesn't need to move about, and its existence is not in danger. The negative, on the other hand, is in danger. It has become unmanifested. It has become polluted. Its very form becomes contaminated. The inner body of an unholy human being is the result of a breakdown in balance between the outer and the spiritual dimensions of Being. The unenlightened, on the other hand, is a reflection of the presence or, more accurately, a projection of the Unmanifested. The Unmanifested is always seeking, always seeking, always seeking; the unholy human spirit has always sought, and has found, a place for itself in the Unmanifested. Only through the realization of the Unmanifested is peace and the realization of peace can the inner body be free of the suffering of unhappiness and unhappiness can cease to pollute. The Unmanifested is always seeking to be free of the illusory form and to become free of form. Only through the realization of the Unmanifested does the unholy human spirit free itself of form and free itself of illusory form. Only through the realization of the Unmanifested can there be inner peace. When you realize that there is only inner peace, the inner body can also free of form and free of illusory form. Otherwise, unhappiness and unhappiness always continue to pollute the outer world. An unholy human person, being deeply unhappy, is in danger of becoming polluted by inner body pollution. Only through the realization of the Unmanifested can peace be realized. Only through the realization of peace can the unholy human spirit free itself of inner pollution. It is also through enlightenment that the unholy human spirit can free itself of its illusory form and become free of form. Only through enlightenment do you realize that form and formlessness have nothing to do with one another. Form is part of formless Being. Forms are part of formless consciousness. Neither form nor formlessness can exist without the other. You cannot have form without knowing it. You cannot have true inner peace without knowing your inner peace. The purpose of this book is to show you how to be in touch with your true nature as well as the unfathomable Source that is your true nature. This will free you from the delusion that because you know your true nature and your true nature knows you, you must become conscious of it, so that you can have inner peace, inner peace, inner peace. Only through the realization of the Unmanifested does peace become possible. Only through the realization of peace does peace come into being. Only through the realization of peace does you begin to realize your true nature as well as the unfathomable Source from which you derive your peace. Through the realization of truth, you can then become yourself again and truly free from form and formlessness.”

VIII. CONCLUSIONS & CAVEATS

In conclusion, during this project the researcher recognized that some of the books used during the pruning may require a re-write given the writing style used by the user, especially the instances where the author has used a prominent first-person narration style. It may require further training and extended research for the development of a Corpora under each genre required. Further multiple preprocessing may be required depending on the model evaluation results.

This paper presents a comprehensive approach for manual corpora development for Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPT) and evaluating the model's learning capability. The study shows that the accuracy and relevance of the GPT model's output depend significantly on the quality of the training data and the techniques used during training. The researchers manually audited and refined a set of books to develop a corpus suitable for GPT2 (Medium Size) training. The model was trained on the refined corpus, and the accuracy and relevance of the generated content were evaluated using different tests, including cosine similarity and semantic similarity tests. The findings of this study provide a tested framework for the preparation and training of a GPT-2 model that can generate more relevant and accurate content. The authors also demonstrate the model's output in action through a GUI that allows users to enter a topic and generate content based on the corpus. Overall, this paper contributes to the understanding of the importance of data quality and preprocessing criteria in the development of GPT models and provides a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners in this field.

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